

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Inheritance of hybrid weakness in indica/japonica rice crosses

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We investigated the inheritance of hybrid weakness occurring in F₂, F₃, and subsequent generations in remote crosses of rice.

The F₁ plants of indica (IR24, CR44, Milyang 23, and Suweon 258) and japonica varieties from Japan showed vigorous growth and partial sterility.

The weak segregants in F₂ were slightly yellow at the seedling stage. Fresh weight of their aboveground phytomass 60 d after transplanting averaged about one-tenth as much as that of normal plants. Some of them died before heading. Mature plants were stunted and had only a few short panicles. Numbers of normal and weak plants observed in six F₂ populations are given in Table 1. The relative frequency of weak segregants was 2.2 to 7.5%, which fit the expected frequency of 6.3% under a duplicate recessive gene system.

In the F₃ lines derived from randomly sampled F₂ plants of Toyonishiki/Milyang 23, 27 lines produced all normal plants, 11 lines segregated 15 normal to 1 weak, 14 lines segregated 3 normal to 1 weak, and 2 lines produced all weak plants. This segregation pattern gave a good fit to the expected 7:4:41 (c² = 1.5238, 0.60 < P < 0.70).

The BC₁F₁ plants were all normal. The segregation of BC₁F₂ lines gave a good fit to the expected 2 (all normal):1 (segregating 15:1) : 1 (segregating 3:1) ratio in all crosses (Table 2).

A duplicate recessive gene system in which double recessive homozygotes express weakness can be adapted to these segregation patterns. This is a new

Table 1. Segregation for hybrid weakness in F₂ populations.

Cross combination	Plants (no.)			Weak plants (%)	χ^2 (15:1)	P (df=1)
	Normal	Weak	Total			
Reimei/IR24	128	4	132	3.03	2.3354	0.10-0.20
CR44/Reimei	319	26	345	7.54	0.9741	0.30-0.40
Akiahikari/Milyang 23	131	3	134	2.22	3.6796	0.05-0.10
Toyonishiki/Milyang 23	132	8	140	5.71	0.0686	0.75-0.80
Milyang 23/IG-15 ^a	631	35	666	5.26	1.1247	0.25-0.30
Reimei/Suweon 258	129	3	132	2.27	3.5636	0.05-0.10

^a IG-15 = Ishiokamochi 15.

Table 2. Segregation for hybrid weakness in BC₁F₁ populations and BC₁F₂ lines.

Cross combination ^a	Plants in BC ₁ F ₁ populations (no.)		BC ₁ F ₂ lines (no.) with the ratio (normal:weak)			χ^2 (2:1:1)	P (df=2)
	Normal	Weak	1:0	15:1	3:1		
Reimei/M23/M23	28	0	16	7	5	0.8571	0.60-0.70
Reimei/M23/Reimei	92	0	53	19	20	2.1522	0.30-0.40
M23/Akiahikari/M23	18	0	8	6	4	0.6667	0.70-0.75
M23/Toyonishiki/M23	48	0	25	10	13	0.4583	0.75-0.80
S258/Reimei/S258	34	0	21	6	7	1.9412	0.30-0.40
Reimei/S258/Reimei	40	0	22	9	9	0.4000	0.80-0.90
Reimei/IR24/IR24	20	0	13	4	3	1.9000	0.30-0.40
Reimei/IR24/Reimei	34	0	17	10	7	0.5294	0.75-0.80
CR44/Reimei/CR44	46	0	22	15	9	1.6522	0.40-0.50

^a M23 = Milyang 23, S258 = Suweon 258.

genic system for hybrid weakness in remote crosses of rice. Hybrid breakdown in F₂ and later inbred generations due to hybrid weakness and partial sterility

would eliminate desirable recombinants and distort segregations of genes in breeding programs using indica-japonica hybridization. □

Breeding methods

Inheritance of a low-tillering plant type in rice

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A major gene controlling the low tillering trait was found in Japanese variety

Aikawa 1. This spontaneous mutant was discovered by a Japanese farmer in 1980. Restricted tillering, long and thick culms, and dense panicles are the mutant-type characters that distinguish the variety's plant type.

We investigated the inheritance mode of the plant type using a cross between Aikawa 1 and Chiyonishiki, which is

Table 1. Characteristics of plant type components of Aikawa 1, Chiyonishiki, and their F₁.^a

Variety	Days to heading (no.)	Culm length (cm)	Panicles per plant (no.)	Diameter of main culm ^b (mm)	Panicle characters					Weight of a brown rice grain (mg)
					Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets (no.)	Seed fertility (%)	Primary branches (no.)	Secondary branches (no.)	
Aikawa 1	98.0	93.6	4.9	10.00	21.7	221.4	87.4	16.3	45.4	23.3
Chiyonishiki	103.0	76.5	11.8	5.37	18.3	97.1	96.9	9.5	16.3	22.4
F ₁	96.0 (96)	91.4 (108)	8.4 (101)	7.92 (103)	20.7 (104)	182.6 (115)	91.0 (99)	14.0 (109)	36.8 (119)	23.1 (101)

^a Figures in parentheses are percentages of F₁ compared with the midparent. ^b Measured at the central part of the fifth internode.

Table 2. Phenotypic correlations among plant type characters of the Aikawa 1/Chiyonishiki F₃ lines (n = 69).

Character ^a	Culm length (CL)	Panicle length (PL)	Panicles per plant (NP)	Total weight (TW)	Panicle weight (PW)	Harvest index (HI)	Single panicle weight (SPW)	Spikelets per panicle (NS)	Panicle density (PD)	Days to heading (NHD)
PL	0.442									
NP	-0.891	-0.446								
TW	-0.378	0.118	0.636							
PW	-0.348	0.256	0.567	0.960						
HI	0.089	0.500	-0.209	-0.081	0.194					
SPW	0.903	0.614	-0.914	-0.335	-0.248	0.308				
NS	0.869	0.624	-0.875	-0.341	-0.244	0.348	0.952			
PD	0.884	0.507	-0.887	-0.398	-0.316	0.291	0.939	0.990		
NHD	0.624	0.177	-0.452	-0.010	-0.046	-0.093	0.513	0.467	0.488	
PTI	0.858	0.467	-0.910	-0.503	-0.442	0.218	0.949	0.908	0.913	0.434

^a PTI (plant type index) = SPW/NP × 100. PD = NS/PL. Pr[|r| > 0.237] = 0.05, Pr[|r| > 0.3081] = 0.01, df = 67.

high-tillering and short-statured. F₁, F₂, and F₃ plants were transplanted. F₁ plants had intermediate plant type (Table 1). Mutant-type characters showed incomplete dominance in the F₁. Each character had a segregation ratio of 3 mutant:1 normal in the F₂. These mutant characters were completely associated in

the F₂ and F₃ plants. Thus F₂ segregated into 358:112 (mutant:normal), and gave a good fit to 3:1 ratio ($\chi^2 = 0.3433, 0.50 < P < 0.60$).

The F₃ lines derived from randomly sampled F₂ plants segregated into 23:31:15 (mutant:segregating:normal), and gave a good fit to a 1:2:1 ratio ($\chi^2 =$

2.913, 0.20 < P < 0.30). Several plant type characters, such as panicles per plant, spikelets per panicle, and culm length, showed either highly positive or negative correlations in the F₃ lines (Table 2). A single semidominant gene controls the low tillering trait, and this gene has pleiotropic effects on culm length and thickness, and panicle density.

Aikawa 1 and the true breeding F₃ lines of the mutant type had long culms that were very thick and sturdy and therefore resistant to lodging. These plants showed high seed fertility, erect leaf habit, and normal plant and grain development. The presence of these traits distinguishes this source of a major genic low tillering habit from others previously reported.

We are conducting yield trials under direct seeded conditions using several pairs of lines that are near isogenic except for the low tillering trait. □

Grain quality

Test of three rice grain quality characteristics

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We randomly chose 86 rice varieties of different origins from the International Rice Germplasm Center of IRRI and Hubei Province and used standard tests to determine amylose content (AC), gelatinization temperature (GT), and gel consistency (GC).

Distribution and performance of rice grain quality characteristics were country or region specific to some extent (see figure). In general, Japanese rice had low AC, low GT, and soft GC; most Korean rice had low AC and low to intermediate GT; IRRI (Philippine) varieties usually had high AC, low GT, and varying GC; Chinese varieties had varied characteristics across the four subgroups.

Samples from Japan, Korea, and central China had the most acceptable characteristics for japonica varieties: low to medium AC, low to intermediate GT,

Correlation coefficients among three quality characteristics by group.^a

Group or subgroup	Samples ^b (no.)	Examples	Correlation		
			AC—GT	AC—GC	GT—GC
IRRI	n ₁ = 22	IR8, IR20, IR36, IR54	-0.26	-0.45*	-0.15
	n ₂ = 23		-0.27	-0.39	-0.1
Japan	n ₁ = 10	Norin 9, Akage, Kuromochi	0	-0.61*	0
	n ₂ = 11		0	-0.59*	0
Korea	n ₁ = 9	Suk Na, Banto Kanon	0.53	-0.69*	-0.24
	n ₂ = 10		0.25	-0.80**	-0.02
China	n ₁ = 39		-0.68**	-0.85**	0.59**
	n ₂ = 42		-0.24	-0.85**	0.32*
Northern China	n ₁ = 10	Ta Ma Gu Chuan Nien	-0.97**	-0.92**	0.82**
Southern China	n ₁ = 9	Fu Lu Tsan, Chiu Erh Ai, Chen Ma Ai	-0.02	-0.10	-0.87**
	n ₂ = 10		0.79**	-0.83**	-0.95**
Central China	n ₁ = 11	Keng 73, E Yi 105, Yu Dao	0.24	-0.68*	-0.69*
	n ₂ = 13		0.78**	-0.87**	-0.78**
Taiwan	n = 9	Chianan 2, Liu Chow	-0.73*	-0.78*	0.64
Total	n ₁ = 80		-0.12	-0.53**	0.26*
	n ₂ = 86		-0.11	-0.59**	0.21

^a *, ** = significant difference at 5% and 1% levels. ^b n₂ = n₁ + waxy varieties if present.

and soft to medium GC, the result of selecting to meet the preferences of consumers.

Some associations existed among the three characteristics though they differed with rice group and if waxy varieties